

RESIDUAL STRESSES IN THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES: Experimental Techniques

Patricia P. Parlevliet, Harald E.N. Bersee, Adriaan Beukers

*Faculty of Aerospace Engineering, Delft University of Technology
Kluyverweg 1, 2629 HS Delft, The Netherlands*

SUMMARY: Experimental techniques based on the curvature of unbalanced laminates were developed to study residual stresses in thermoplastic composites. The method utilises the Process Simulated Laminate (PSL) technique as developed by Manson and Seferis [1] in order to check on the residual stress distribution through the thickness of a balanced laminate. The resulting curvatures after layer removal are measured by means of Grid Analysis by photogrammetry. The photogrammetry method was validated by measuring the curvatures of a standard unbalanced cross-ply laminate with other means and the results showed good correlation.

KEYWORDS: Residual stresses, thermoplastic composites, process simulated laminate, curvature, photogrammetry.

INTRODUCTION

Background

Increasing amounts of continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites are being applied in aircraft structures. Arguments for using thermoplastic matrices instead of thermoset matrices are mostly economical of nature: thermoplastic composites can be formed and consolidated in several minutes whereas the thermoset composites need a time-consuming cure cycle. Besides, thermoplastics are known for their weldability, toughness, long (indefinite) storage life, recyclability and chemical resistance. However, after processing and subsequent cooling of composite laminates from the relatively high processing temperature to the service temperature, thermal residual stresses arise due to the mismatch in coefficient of thermal expansion between the fibres and the matrix and between plies at different angles with respect to each other. The stresses may lead to dimensional changes, lower ultimate strength and premature initial cracking of the matrix and fibre-matrix interface. Since residual stresses are inherently present in virtually all composites and influence the properties of the composite structures significantly, it is of most importance that the residual thermal stresses are taken into account in both design and analytic modelling of composite structures. However, first the magnitude of residual stresses must be known by either prediction or experimental measurements. Predictive models need validation by experimental values, and these are not yet readily available for thermoplastic composites. This study aims to develop easy-to-use experimental techniques that can be used to determine the residual strains in balanced thermoplastic composite laminates.

Experimental Techniques

Many experimental techniques for measuring thermal residual strains and stresses have been developed in the past [2, 3]. Most of these techniques provide an insight in the magnitude of residual stresses in laminates in an indirect manner, like first ply failure method and measurement of curvature of unbalanced laminates. Direct strain measurements are mostly performed on micro-scale composites. Development of more advanced analytical apparatus made it possible to directly measure the residual strain development in a full-scale composite during the cool-down process [4]. Although the distinction between direct and indirect techniques is made up by the author, dividing the techniques in these two groups seems reasonable with the application of the following definitions: direct experimental techniques for determination of the magnitude of residual stresses provides a quantity that can directly be translated to residual strains in one of the composites' constituents. Indirect techniques measure a quantity that need to be translated to a residual stress magnitude based on a prediction or estimation of the dependency of the residual stresses on that parameter. Both groups encompass techniques that provide (an estimation of) the magnitude of the residual stresses on the three levels of origin of residual stresses: ply level or micro-mechanical level; the laminate residual stresses on a meso-mechanical level; and the residual stress distribution through-the-thickness of the laminate or the macro-mechanical level.

The simplest means that can be used to assess the magnitude of the residual stresses is the use of unbalanced cross-ply or angle-ply laminates [5], which develop a curvature, because the residual stresses can partially be relieved by out-of-plane deformations [6]. Depending on the dimensions of the laminate, often a cylindrical shape is obtained [7]. The curvature is related to the magnitude of residual stresses [8] and can be estimated using either a bimetallic strip analysis [8]; a linear elastic relation [9] or a modified classical lamination theory [3, 7, 10-13]. This method is easy-to-use and most often applied in literature, which makes it ideal as a reference technique.

A variation on the curvature technique is trying to obtain unsymmetrical laminates by removing one or more layers from a balanced (flat) laminate. The resulting curvatures can be used to calculate the residual stresses before layer removal [14]. Layer removal is often accomplished by abrasion, which can cause degradation by heat introduction or microcracking of the composite. Manson and Seferis [1] described the concept of the Process Simulated Laminate (PSL), which offers the possibility to determine the laminate residual stresses and the skin-core residual stresses, without damaging the composite as in layer removal by abrasion. The PSL technique consists of several composite prepreg plies separated by release plies, most often polyimide foils. The plies between two separation films form a Constitutive Laminate (CL), see Fig.1 and these CL's can be separated after processing and analysed. The residual stress distribution can be determined by measuring the dimensional changes (curvature) of the PSL and CL's before and after separation.

Fig. 1: Laminate skin-core residual stress distribution (grey area), after [1].

The separation film is the critical constituent in the PSL technique, because the film must enable “perfect” adhesion to the composite for load transfer and it must allow separation from the composite after the processing step. In addition, it must not interfere in any way in the residual stress formation, through for example degradation, initiation of additional forces, and should not create residual stresses itself due to thermal expansion mismatch. These requirements make it difficult to find a suitable release film for the matrix material under investigation. Especially the adhesion during processing requirement can prove to be challenging. Manson and Seferis tried a number of possible films (aluminium foil, Kapton®, PA-6 all with and without release agent), and found for their material (AS4/Polyetheretherketone) the Kapton® foil to work best. It was shown that the influence of the film on temperature and residual stress build up could be neglected.

Curvature measurements can be performed in several ways, with the most common technique being cutting of the laminate in thin strips, and measuring the deflection in the centre of the specimen h and the chord length of the specimen L , see Fig. 2 [5, 6, 8, 10, 15-18].

Fig. 2: Measurement of curvature, after [6].

The radius of curvature ρ can then be calculated with:

$$\rho = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{L^2}{4h} + h \right) \quad (1)$$

The dimensionless curvature $t\kappa$ defined as the thickness t multiplied by the curvature (or thickness divided by the radius) was most often used, because it directly relates to the amount of differential thermal shrinkage which can induce residual stresses, eliminating the effects of thickness variation from specimen to specimen [8, 16, 18]. Often the curvature of the strip edge (deflection) was measured using a travelling microscope [5, 6, 8], measuring microscope [1], a cathetometer [17], or with a dial micrometer fixed between two pins [18] and the chord length with a steel ruler [8].

Determination of the shape of the whole composite laminate was also performed [7, 19] by measuring the out-of-plane displacement in the x - and y -directions with a dial gauge [7] or at several positions on straight lines without contact, to ensure that the measuring technique did not cause deflections of the thin laminates [3]. In addition, many techniques measuring the out-of-plane deflection based on interferometry were used [20-22]. It was observed [19] that the laminates were not perfectly cylindrical, because they showed some free-edge effects, hence Unger and Hansen [16] performed curvature measurements on non-symmetric laminates after sides were trimmed to remove edge-affected material.

One other method that can be used to detect the curvature of the cylinder is photogrammetry or square grid analysis [23, 24]. This method simply takes two pictures from different angles

of the three-dimensional specimens, which have been prepared by applying a grid on the surface, for instance using a sticker with a grid printed on it. In the photographs, a reference item (the target) is included, e.g. a cube with a grid of known dimensions. During analysis, the target is used to define a coordinate system and to calibrate the photographs for the dimensions. Then, the grid points on the sample are identified and computer analysis of the photographs results in the coordinates of the grid points. From these coordinates, curvatures can be determined by mapping them onto a circle by, for example, a least-squares method [23, 24].

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Materials

Rolls of unidirectional (UD) carbon fibre (AS4) reinforced polyetherimide (PEI, Ultem® 1000) and polyetheretherketone (PEEK) prepregs were supplied by Cytec Engineered Materials, USA, with a resin content of 34.2% and 34% respectively. The prepreg layers had a non-consolidated thickness of 0.21 mm. The 25 µm thick Upilex® (Polyimide, PI) release film was obtained from Ube Technologies, Japan and the aluminium foil was a common 20 µm thick aluminium foil. 80 µm thick glass reinforced PTFE (Bisca-tex® 08-150) was obtained from Biscor S.A.R.L., France. The polyimide and aluminium foils were impregnated with Semiperm® 4.5GS release agent during some tests.

As stated before, the release film should be able to transfer (interlaminar shear) loads during processing, but accommodate easy peeling of layers after processing. In order to identify suitable combinations of composite material and foil, several material combinations were tried in a preliminary test programme. In this programme, only cross-ply laminates were produced, as this will yield maximum stresses on the foil. Adhesion of the foil to the composite plies after processing was used as an indicator for the ability to transfer loads through the foil during processing. The feasibility for peeling was investigated by peeling the layers apart by hand. It was previously shown [1, 25] that for PEEK composites, polyimide (PI) foil was a good choice, however, for composites with other matrices, the most suitable foil was not yet identified. A short program to find the best combinations with the above-mentioned foils, found that polyimide foils without release agent for AS4/PEEK as well as for AS4/PEI laminates provided the best combination.

Specimen Preparation

The dimensions of the composites were chosen such that a cylindrical shape would be the result [7]. Specimens are prepared using a brass picture frame (inside dimensions 2x120x100 mm) mould (coated with release agent) to prevent flow of matrix and fibres. The picture frame with the specimens was placed between two aluminium plates. The thickness of the samples can vary up to 2 mm (the thickness of the mould) and a plunger is needed for samples below 2 mm thickness, in order to apply the necessary pressure. A hot platen press was used to consolidate the specimens and the processing cycles for every material are depicted in Table 1.

Table 1. Processing cycles

Material	Processing temperature	Pressure [MPa]	Pressure holding time	Cooling rate
AS4/PEEK	390 °C	0.2	10 min	35°C/min
AS4/PEI	330 °C	0.5	10 min	35°C/min

The single UD plies and foils are cut to size by hand. The AS4/PEI plies are dried overnight before stacking the plies in the mould. A cross-ply lay-up was chosen to obtain maximum residual stresses due to the highest difference in coefficient of thermal expansion in the two directions. Three lay-ups were chosen to perform the various experiments with; see Table 2, where PI represents the place of the Polyimide foil. The thicknesses of the consolidated curved laminates were measured with an accuracy of 0.025 mm.

Table 2. Specimens

Specimen number	Materials	Lay-up	Consolidated laminate thickness
I	AS4/PEEK	0/90/90/PI/0	0.53/PI/0.16 mm
II	AS4/PEI	0/90/PI/90/0	0.27/PI/0.27 mm
III	AS4/PEI	0/90	0.27 mm

After processing, the samples are inspected for small ridges that might have resulted from material flowing into the gap between the plunger and the picture frame. If present, these edges are removed to prevent their geometrical stiffness from influencing the curvature of the sample.

Test set-up

For the photogrammetry experiments, the grid was applied by printing it on a sticker and taping that sticker to the curved specimen under investigation. The grid lines were positioned in such a way, that they were parallel and perpendicular to the fibre 90° and 0° axes, respectively and that edges ± 10 mm from the sides were disregarded, because of the edge effects, see Fig. 4. A target of known dimensions is put next to the sample for calibration of the photographs. In order to obtain reproducible results, a set up was build to control the camera angles. This set-up consisted of a turntable, on which a three-point support was made for the sample; see Fig. 3. In addition, a support for the target was created, in order to align the target with the sample, which makes analysis of multiple samples easier. The photogrammetric method was tested using a PVC cylinder of known dimension. This test showed that from the photographs the radius could be determined with an accuracy of 0.25%. Photographs were taken of grids placed on the composite samples after removal of the polyimide foil, in order to measure the curvature due to release of the residual stresses.

Fig. 3: Photogrammetry test set-up.

Fig. 4. Example of photographs used for photogrammetry experiments.

Two other curvature-measuring techniques were applied to one “standard” sample, a 0/90/90 AS4/PEEK laminate from which a 0° ply was released with the PSL method, to compare the various experimental values. First, the curvature was measured along the same three lines on the grid as applied for the photogrammetry set-up with a tip probe and an x - y distance measuring table. Next, the dimensionless curvature on the edge of the specimens was measured as in Fig. 2, after cutting the laminate in strips along the same three lines. The cylindrical edges were photographed on the two sides that resulted from one cut, with an Olympus C350Z digital camera (3.1 mega-pixel). The image was copied to a Matlab® program and the height h , the length $2L$ and thickness t were measured in pixels. The dimensionless curvature t/ρ was calculated using Eqn. 1. Measurement of the curvature with the three techniques on the standard sample was performed in one day, to make sure the laminates did not relax in between measurements. Besides, the laminates were already allowed to relax during one month after processing.

Calculations

The measured curvatures will be used to estimate the residual stresses σ_R that would exist perpendicular to the fibres in a similar symmetrical laminate of thickness $2t$ using Eqn.2 developed by [8] based on an analysis of bimetallic strip by Timoshenko [5, 6, 13, 26]:

$$\sigma_R = \frac{(E_1 \times E_2)}{(E_1 + E_2)} \cdot \frac{t}{\rho} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{24} \left(2 + \frac{E_1}{E_2} + \frac{E_2}{E_1} \right) \right) \quad (2)$$

where E_1 and E_2 are the longitudinal and transverse moduli, respectively of the ply [6]. This equation may be used when assumed that the plies are of equal thickness [6], which for specimen I is not the case. An appropriate model is under investigation, however, calculations with Eqn. 2 are performed for illustrative purposes. Moduli for AS4/PEEK and AS4/PEI plies were obtained from the supplier [27, 28]: AS4/PEEK: $E_1 = 138$ GPa; $E_2 = 10.2$ GPa, AS4/PEI: $E_1 = 130$ GPa; $E_2 = 9$ GPa.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A plot of the coordinates found with photogrammetry and the probe tip method showed that the inspected area of the laminates deforms cylindrically, hence taking the radius as part of a circle is allowed. The found dimensionless radii of curvature as measured with the three different methods are depicted in Table 3. The radii and thicknesses of the curved laminates are obtained from the photographs and are measured in pixels, hence the dimensionless curvatures t/ρ are directly calculated.

Table 3. Curvatures as measured with different techniques

Method	Radius/ curvature			Average radius \pm stdev	Dimensionless curvature t/ρ ($\cdot 10^{-3}$)
	Row 1	Row 2	Row 3		
Photogrammetry (Radius ρ)	38.42 mm	38.47 mm	38.12 mm	38.37 \pm 0.19 mm	13.83 \pm 0.07
Probe tip (Radius ρ)	39.67 mm	39.51 mm	39.55 mm	39.57 \pm 0.09 mm	13.39 \pm 0.03
Photographs (dimensionless curvature)	0.0124 0.0144	0.0118 0.0120	0.0113 0.0144		12.7 \pm 1.4

As the results in the last column in Table 3 show, the measured dimensionless curvatures are in good agreement with each other with a maximum difference of 8.2% between the photogrammetry method and the strip curvature (as measured by digital photography) method. The photogrammetry method and probe tip measurements provide most accuracy (a standard deviation of 0.5 and 0.2%, respectively).

The curvatures as measured with the photogrammetry method and calculated residual stresses for the three specimens are described in Table 4. The plies in between brackets are the removed plies.

Table 4. Photogrammetry curvatures

Specimen	Radius ρ [mm]			Average [mm]	t [mm]	σ_R [MPa]
	Row 1	Row 2	Row 3			
I: 0/90/90(/PI/0) PEEK	38.42	38.47	38.12	38.37 \pm 0.19	0.53	*150.9 \pm 0.7
II: 0/90(/PI/90/0) PEI	57.08	58.18	56.24	57.16 \pm 0.97	0.27	47.2 \pm 0.8
III: 0/90 PEI	53.81	53.59	52.09	53.16 \pm 0.94	0.27	50.8 \pm 0.9

*: Eqn. 2 can probably not be applied due to the differences in thickness of the 0° and 90°-plies, however, the calculated value is included here for illustrative purposes.

As can be seen in Table 4 for specimens II and III, the resulting curvature for a 0/90 constitutive laminate (CL) from a balanced 0/90/PI/90/0 laminate is significantly different than for a 0/90 CL where no layers were removed. The same was checked for the PEEK composite, and a different curvature was found for the 0/90/90 laminate from which no layers were removed (not measured with the photogrammetry method, hence not given here). In addition, it can be observed that the PEI composites show much less curvature than the PEEK composites, which can be attributed to the level of residual stresses due to higher amount of shrinkage of the PEEK matrix, because of the semi-crystallinity of the PEEK matrix.

DISCUSSION

The curvatures as measured with the photogrammetry and probe tip method agree very well, and the accuracy is high. The dimensionless curvatures as measured with the digital photographs taken of the cylindrical cut edges show much scatter as was already pointed out in literature [13]. One of the limiting factors here are the dimensions of the pixels. The tip probe method is very time-consuming and with the proper data-recognition system, the photogrammetry method is very rapid and accurate.

The question whether the PSL method is applicable still needs to be addressed by comparing the residual stresses calculated from the resulting curvatures to predictions of the residual stresses by means of the Classical Lamination Theory. This will be part of future work.

According to Eijpe [3] the curvatures of a 0/90 laminate should be the same as a symmetrical 0/90/90/0 laminate after removal of the 0/90 constitutive laminate. However, in this study a difference in 0/90 curvature in specimens II and III is observed. This may be attributed to the presence of the rigid mould on both sides of the 0/90 laminate and the absence of the rigid mould/ press plate on one side of the 0/90 CL in the 0/90/90/0 laminate. A rigid mould may have a very significant influence on thin laminates, since it prevents a relative large portion of the laminate from deforming freely. In addition, the difference in thickness might have resulted in a different cooling profile through the thickness of the laminate. However, in literature for these thin laminates no temperature gradient was found upon cooling [25]. Further research is necessary to identify the exact influence of the release foil, although in literature [1, 25] it was concluded that the polyimide release foil has no thermal and mechanical influence on the residual stress formation.

The curvatures measured in this research were found to be much higher than the curvatures previously measured in literature [5, 6, 13], which may be attributed to the high cooling rate used in this study.

CONCLUSIONS

Photogrammetry has proven a strong tool to measure differences in out-of-plane displacements. This project utilised this tool successfully to determine the resulting curvatures in constitutive laminates, as formed with the PSL method, in order to determine the residual strains on a meso-mechanical level. The correlation between the curvatures obtained with photogrammetry, tip probe and strip curvature was excellent.

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